

Technical Note

Human Reliability Assessment and Human Performance Evaluation: Research and Analysis Activities at the U.S. NRC

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Within the context of the NRC charter to ensure adequate protection of the public health and safety, the common defense and security, and the environment in the use of nuclear materials in the United States, the mission of NRC activities concerning human reliability assessment and human performance evaluation is to ensure effective regulation and oversight of licensee personnel performance.

Five general strategies for achieving the mission are listed below.

1. Conduct event analyses and operational experience reviews to focus agency attention on current and developing human performance concerns with facility operations and maintenance and with issues associated with transport and storage of nuclear waste.
2. Develop guidance on regulatory issues concerning the performance of licensee personnel consistent with the philosophy of risk-informed and performance-based regulation. Conduct inspections and reviews of issues associated with human performance and reliability at nuclear power plants and materials licensees consistent with this guidance.
3. Conduct research to better understand those factors that influence human reliability and performance to support the development of guidance and regulatory positions.
4. Develop and maintain methods to understand and describe the impact of human performance and reliability on operational safety and public risk.

5. Provide technical expertise in the areas of human reliability assessment and human performance evaluation by establishing mechanisms for dialogue and cooperation, both nationally and internationally.

Five research and analysis programs have been identified to implement the strategies discussed above. These include:

Program 1. Conduct Operating Events Analysis and Data Base Maintenance to Support Human Performance Evaluation and Human Reliability Analysis

Program 2. Develop the Technical Basis to Support Human Performance Evaluation and Human Reliability Analysis

Program 3. Develop the Technical Basis and Guidance on Management and Organizational Influences in Human Performance and Plant Risk

Program 4. Develop and Maintain an Integrated Model of Human Performance and Human Reliability

Program 5. Establish a National and International Dialogue and Cooperation on Human Performance Evaluation and Human Reliability Analysis Methods and Data

Each of these programs is discussed in some detail below.

Program 1. Conduct Operating Events Analysis and Data Base Maintenance to Support Human Performance Evaluation and Human Reliability Analysis

The purpose of this program is to conduct event analyses and operational experience reviews to focus agency attention on current and developing human performance concerns with nuclear power plant management, operations, and maintenance and on similar issues associated with the transport, use and storage of nuclear materials. This program also includes maintaining a consolidated, human performance data base that enhances understanding of those factors that influence human behavior and their impact on licensee performance and public risk and that supports inspection and review activities.

All activities in this program area will accomplish one or more of the following objectives:

1. Contribute to the understanding of human performance and human reliability through event analyses and the development of event analyses guidance.
2. Supply human performance information to expand the integrated human reliability model (i.e., the ATHEANA model described in NRC report NUREG-6350).
3. Support establishment of a consolidated, agency-wide human performance database.
4. Contribute to the integration of event analysis findings to risk-informed and performance-based regulatory activities involving human performance and human reliability.

Program 2. Develop the Technical Basis to Support Human Performance Evaluation and Human Reliability Analysis

The purpose of this program is to develop the technical basis and guidance for evaluating human factors issues (such as procedures, training, human-system interface, staffing, work scheduling, environmental stressors, and ergonomics) and their effects on human performance and human reliability of power plant and materials licensees. Additionally, this program will evaluate the influence of advanced control and display technologies on human performance and reliability in NPP operation.

All activities in this program area will accomplish one or more of the following objectives:

1. Improve the understanding of human factors issues and their effects on human performance and human reliability.
2. Improve the understanding of the influence of advanced control and display technologies on human performance and human reliability.
3. Contribute to the integration of human factors principles into risk-informed and performance-based regulation.
4. Conduct evaluations and develop recommendations, as requested, on NRC's in-house human performance issues.

Program 3. Develop the Technical Basis and Guidance on Management and Organizational Influences in Human Performance and Plant Risk

The purpose of this program is to develop the technical basis and guidance to support: 1) the identification and quantification of important management and organizational influences, including the effects of deregulation, downsizing, and decommissioning on human performance, human reliability and plant safety;

2) the conduct of inspection activities, event investigations, data collection and other regulatory activities associated with management and organization issues at NPPs; and, 3) the integration of management and organization issues into risk-informed and performance-based regulation.

All activities in this program area will accomplish one or more of the following objectives:

1. Help identify important management and organization influences on human performance, human reliability, and plant safety.
2. Improve the ability to model and quantify management and organization factors as part of a human reliability analysis.
3. Support development of guidance for identifying important management and organization factors during inspection and review activities, event investigations, data collection, and other regulatory activities.
4. Contribute to the integration of management and organization issues in risk-informed and performance-based regulatory activities.

Program 4. Develop and Maintain an Integrated Model of Human Performance and Human Reliability

The purpose of this program is to continue development of and to maintain an integrated model of human performance and human reliability to support probabilistic risk assessment. This model will address issues that have an important effect on human performance and human reliability, will guide the identification and quantification of human errors including errors of commission, and will be valid

for describing human performance and human reliability in a broad spectrum of high-technology environments. This model will serve also as the framework to guide future agency activities associated with the Human Performance Evaluation and Human Reliability Analysis Initiative.

All activities in this program area will accomplish one or more of the following objectives:

1. Develop the technical basis for a model of human reliability by providing an understanding of the nexus between the risk to public safety and issues relating to human reliability among licensee personnel.
2. Apply the human reliability model to agency and licensee human reliability analysis activities and in the transition to risk-informed and performance-based regulation.
3. Apply the human reliability model to non-power technologies.
4. Upgrade the human reliability model to address additional human reliability influences (such as management and organizational factors) and to reflect new insights from research findings and events analyses from the non-nuclear as well as nuclear technology industries.

Program 5. Establish National and International Dialogue and Cooperation on Human Performance Evaluation and Human Reliability Analysis Methods and Data

To maximize the effectiveness and efficiency of the initiative discussed here, this program will foster dialogue and cooperation among other agencies and countries and industry groups on issues associated with human performance evaluation, human reliability analysis, research findings, and operational experience.

All activities in this program area will accomplish one or more of the following objectives:

1. Support participation in national and international conferences and working groups to discuss human performance and human reliability issues.
2. Support the discussion of human performance and human reliability issues with universities, other federal agencies, industry groups, and research organizations.
3. Support publication of articles in professional and refereed journals and the review, when requested, of articles submitted for publication.
4. Encourage national and international participation in peer reviews of NRC-sponsored activities in human performance evaluation and human reliability analysis and staff participate in such peer reviews.

The activities associated with each of the five programs summarized above are expected to support an improved global perspective of human factors issues in power generation.